

Integrating Structural Biology Instruct-ULTRA

WP2 – Roadmap to the future for Instruct

Lead Beneficiary: P1-Instruct

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Deliverable: 2.4 – Schedule of events to engage widely with key stakeholders

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Project objective

In its mission to deliver cutting-edge structural biology to pan-European scientists, Instruct-ERIC engages with a wide variety of stakeholders. Stakeholder interactions have many purposes, including dissemination of access and training opportunities from Instruct, sharing news and events with the structural biology community, and garnering membership and funding. To this end, Instruct-ERIC must work to maintain its relationship with established stakeholders, and connect with new audiences to continue to grow its membership and user base. Instruct-ULTRA has dedicated effort to exploring new activities to engage with a variety of Instruct stakeholders in order to make recommendations for future efforts by Instruct-ERIC.

Executive summary

Instruct-ERIC engages with a variety of stakeholders in order to increase awareness and understanding of its important role in the Research Infrastructure landscape and its impact in advancing life science research. Early in the project, Instruct-ULTRA set out an ambitious plan for dissemination and outreach to all of Instruct's key stakeholders (D1.4). Through the combined effort of its partners, Instruct-ULTRA has hosted or otherwise participated in excess of 55 events during RP2, and plans are already in place for participation in at least 25 events during RP3. Stakeholder engagement is, and will continue to be crucial for the long-term sustainability of Instruct-ERIC.

1. Introduction

1.1 Instruct Stakeholders

Instruct needs to engage with a number of different audiences, whose role and influence varies considerably. Of these, there are a number of key stakeholders, whose engagement with Instruct is important for the delivery of its mission and objectives:

- Policy makers and funders
- Government science ministries of potential member countries
- EU/ESFRI
- Industry
- Structural biology community¹
- Life science community¹
- Other research infrastructures
- Instruct users

There are many stakeholders internal to Instruct-ERIC, for example Council members, Executive members, country directors, centre staff, etc. Instruct hosts many events and meetings to cater to its internal stakeholders, however a discussion of these is beyond the scope of the current document.

1.2 Aim of interactions with stakeholders

The aim of engaging with key stakeholders is to increase awareness and understanding of Instruct-ERIC, in particular:

- the quality and scope of the facilities and services that Instruct provides to its target communities
- the value of Instruct to the recipient user community and the reciprocal value of Instruct activities to the members of Instruct
- the importance of democratic access to top quality research infrastructure and expertise to facilitate the generation of high-quality experimental data
- the value of training scientists to exploit fully any new technological advances in the field of structural biology and to emphasise high standard practises
- the impact of structural biology and the role of Instruct in generating new scientific knowledge
- the role of Instruct in demonstrating the value and promoting collaborative science as a 'no-borders' enterprise
- the role of Instruct in forging new relationships and building communities through its actions

¹ Structural biology community and life science community refer to academic scientists working either in the specific field of structural biology or the wider life science community (including biology, chemistry, medical research, plant science). These categories include scientists at all levels, from undergraduate, masters and PhD students, to early-career and post-doctoral researchers, to Principle Investigators (PIs) and professors. Although not sub-categorised in this document, careful thought and attention has been given in event organisation to target different types of scientists.

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The prime purpose of the messages directed at each external audience are summarised in the table below.

Table 1. Key messages for distinct stakeholder groups, taken from the Instruct-ERIC Communications Strategy document.

Audience	Key message
Policy Makers, Funders, EU/ESFRI, Govt Ministries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structural biology is crucial in understanding the basis of health and disease • Instruct-ERIC facilitates high-quality research leading to publication in high-impact journals • Instruct-ERIC allows funders to maximise the impact of their investment by sharing research facilities across borders. • Sustainable funding is needed to maintain long-term effectiveness of Instruct-ERIC. • Showcase your national research on the international stage
Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discover how structural biology can drive innovation and accelerate your research • Reduce in-house investment by exploiting established, Instruct-ERIC state-of-the-art technology through a single point of access. • Discover Instruct-ERIC as a bridge between industry and academia • Solve your research challenges by consulting Instruct-ERIC experts
Established Structural Biologists (group leaders)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take advantage of funding to access world-leading structural biology facilities through Instruct-ERIC. • Strengthen your research group with funded training and internships from Instruct-ERIC. • Explore new and innovative science with R&D awards from Instruct-ERIC • Build and unite the structural biology community through Instruct-ERIC collaborations
Structural Biology community and Instruct users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use Instruct-ERIC's world-class facilities to advance your high-impact science. • Boost your skillset with tailored, hands-on training from leaders in the field • Develop your expertise with an Instruct-ERIC funded placement at a world-leading research facility
Life science community and Instruct users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discover how structural biology can complement your research by offering new insights • Connect with experts in structural biology to guide your scientific investigations • Use Instruct-ERIC world-class facilities to advance your high-impact science • Boost your skillset with tailored, hands-on training from leaders in structural biology

1.3 Activities to engage with stakeholders

There are many different engagement activities through which Instruct can reach its stakeholders - including meetings, conferences and events. Often, the nature and size of the activity will depend on the targeted stakeholder and vice versa. For example, small, intimate meetings are often more appropriate when engaging with influential stakeholders (eg ministry representatives, policy makers, senior scientists), whereas large international conferences are effective at reaching a broad audience of potential Instruct users.

Instruct-ULTRA has organised and hosted a variety of activities, each of which has been designed to capture a particular group of stakeholders. These activities have included Instruct facility launch events for local scientists, industry-targeted networking events, and closed meetings with science ministers of non-Instruct Member countries. Instruct-ULTRA has also created opportunities to participate in events hosted by other networks or organisations, where this is of mutual benefit to Instruct-ERIC and the host organisation. Whilst there are many international networks that host events for the life science and structural biology communities, relatively few are aware of Research Infrastructures or of the role of Instruct-ERIC. As such, Instruct-ULTRA has taken the initiative to engage with external networks, in order that they see the benefit of involving RIs in their activities. We hope that these efforts will lead to wider inclusion of Research Infrastructures in outreach activities, with time dedicated to the dissemination of RI services to the scientific community.

Instruct-ERIC staff also regularly participate at a wide range of European meetings, where key decisions are made about European funding and policy. Such meetings include ESFRI and ERIC Forum meetings.

Within the Instruct-ULTRA dissemination, outreach and exploitation plan (D1.4), plans were set out in the ULTRA project for an extensive conference and meetings schedule. These plans were refined and enlarged, such that a clear conference and meetings schedule was established, beginning July 2018 to run until the end of the project December 2020. Due to the timing of this deliverable D2.4, this document both reports the events which took place July 2018 – December 2019 (RP2) and also describes forward planning for events scheduled for January – December 2020 (RP3),

The following section contains a calendar of selected stakeholder engagement activities in which Instruct has been involved - for example as a meeting host, conference presenter, exhibitor, session sponsor, or participant. Events in RP2 are shaded in blue and those scheduled for RP3 are shaded green.

Some of the key engagement activities are presented as case studies, including a summary and outcome, in Section 3. Events scheduled for RP3 are included in brief, the outcomes of which will be described in future reports.

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ICRI 2018	Conference	11-14 Sep 2018	AT	Instruct-ERIC	Participant									
ELRIG: Drug discovery	Conference	9-10 Oct 2018	GB	Instruct-ULTRA	Participant									
2 nd Instruct Workshop on CryoEM Best Practices	Workshop	15-16 Oct 2018	NL	Instruct-ULTRA / Instruct-NL	Host									
Day of National Research Infrastructures, Czech Republic 2018	Conference	6 Nov 2019	CZ	Instruct-CZ	Presentation									
PSDI 2018	Conference	11-13 Nov 2018	FR	Instruct-NL	Presentation									
2 nd Structural Biology Meeting	Conference	15-16 Nov 2018	SK	Instruct-ULTRA / Instruct-ERIC	Host									
ESFRI workshop: Monitoring of infrastructures, periodic update of Landmarks, use of KPIs	Workshop	19-20 Nov 2018	IT	Instruct-CZ	Participant									
3 rd ERIC Forum Meeting	Meeting	27-29 Nov 2018	ES	Instruct-ERIC	Participant									
InRoad Final Conference	Conference	12 Dec 2018	BE	Instruct-ERIC	Participant									
4 th FRISBI User Meeting	Meeting	13 Dec 2018	FR	Instruct-FR	Participant									
ESFRI-EOSC Liaison Workshop	Workshop	30 Jan 2019	GB	Instruct-ERIC	Participant									
ERIC-Forum kick off meeting	Meeting	31 Jan – 1 Feb 2019	NL	Instruct-ERIC	Participant									
ELRIG: CRISPR in drug discovery	Conference	27-28 Feb 2019	GB	Instruct-ULTRA	Participant									
EMIM 2019	Conference	19-22 Mar 2019	GB	Instruct-ULTRA	Presentation									
XVI Discussions in Structural Molecular Biology and 3 rd User Meeting of CIISB	Conference / Meeting	21-23 Mar 2019	CZ	Instruct-CZ	Participant									
BMS RI Strategy Meeting	Meeting	22 Mar 2019	NL	Instruct-ERIC	Participant									

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AILM2019	Workshop	29 Mar 2019	FR	Instruct-ERIC	Participant										
PARI III	Conference	8-10 Apr 2019	GB	Instruct-ULTRA	Participant										
Cryo-EM inauguration	Launch event	9-10 Apr 2019	IL	Instruct-IL	Participant										
RICE working group meeting	Meeting	11 Apr 2019	GB	Instruct-ULTRA	Participant										
ESV2019	Conference	28 Apr - 1 May 2019	NL	Instruct-ULTRA	Presentation										
4 th ERIC Forum Meeting	Meeting	7-8 May 2019	NO	Instruct-ERIC	Participant										
Women in Science Workshop	Workshop	22 May 2019	ES	Instruct-ULTRA/ Instruct-ERIC	Host										
Instruct Biennial Structural Biology Conference	Conference	23-24 May 2019	ES	Instruct-ERIC/ Instruct-ULTRA	Host										
iNEXT workshop on integrated methodologies and approaches for structural biology	Workshop	28-31 May 2019	CZ	Instruct-CZ	Presentation										
Instruct-ERIC Council Meeting	Meeting	30-31 May 2019	IT	Instruct-ERIC	Host										
Systems Biology	Meeting	6-7 Jun 2019	IE	Instruct-ERIC	Presentation										
Women in Biotech	Meeting	13 Jun 2019	GB	Instruct-ULTRA	Participant										
Instruct for Industry	Networking event	27 Jun 2019	GB	Instruct-ULTRA	Host										
UKRO Conference	Conference	27-28 Jun 2019	GB	Instruct-ERIC	Participant										
MMC 2019	Conference	1-4 Jul 2019	GB	Instruct-ULTRA	Exhibition booth										
ESFRI Validation Workshop	Workshop	3 Jul 2019	BE	Instruct-ERIC	Participant										
FEBS 2019	Conference	6-11 Jul 2019	PL	Instruct-ULTRA	Presentation Exhibition booth										

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Meeting at the Solaris synchrotron	Meeting	9 Jul 2019	PL	Instruct-ULTRA	Participant									
Life Science RI Strategy Board	Meeting	10-11 Jul 2019	ES	Instruct-ERIC	Participant									
EBSA 2019	Conference	20-26 Jul 2019	ES	Instruct-ULTRA	Session sponsor Presentation									
Slovenian CryoEM inauguration	Launch event	6 Sep 2019	SI	Instruct-ULTRA	Participant									
Meeting Slovenian Ministry of Science	Meeting	7 Sep 2019	SI	Instruct-ULTRA	Participant									
MipTec / BASEL LIFE	Conference	9-12 Sep 2019	CH	Instruct-ULTRA	Exhibition booth									
Exchange of Experience IV	Conference	13-14 Sep 2019	SG	Instruct-ERIC	Presentation									
Research and Innovation Days	Conference	24-26 Sep 2019	BE	Instruct-ERIC	Participant									
ESFRI Strategy Report on RIs	Meeting	25 Sep 2019	BE	Instruct-ERIC	Participant									
Instruct Sustainability Workshop	Workshop	10 Oct 2019	BE	Instruct-ULTRA	Host									
Rendez-vous CARNOT	Conference	16-17 Oct 2019	FR	Instruct-FR2	Exhibition booth									
Meet in Italy for Life Science	Conference	16-18 Oct 2019	IT	Instruct-IT	Presentation									
PSDI 2019	Conference	3-5 Nov 2019	GB	Instruct-UK	Presentation									
3 rd Structural Biology Meeting	Conference	14-15 Nov 2019	SK	Instruct-ULTRA	Participant									
Day of National Research Infrastructures, Czech Republic 2019	Conference	19 Nov 2019	CZ	Instruct-CZ	Presentation									
3 rd Instruct Workshop on CryoEM Best Practices	Workshop	19-20 Nov 2019	FR	Instruct-ULTRA / Instruct-FR1	Host									
Astbury Centre Launch	Launch event	25 Nov 2019	GB	Instruct-ULTRA /	Host									

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				Instruct-UK										
LS RI Board Meeting	Meeting	5 Dec 2019	BE	Instruct-ERIC	Participant									
ASCB EMBO 2019	Conference	8-11 Dec 2019	US	Instruct-ULTRA	Presentation Exhibition booth									
Planned activities														
Instruct meeting at Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore	Meeting	16 Jan 2020	IN	Instruct-ULTRA	Participant									
Instruct meeting at Indian Council of Medical Research, Delhi	Meeting	17 Jan 2020	IN	Instruct-ULTRA	Participant									
HyThaBio scientific meeting	Workshop	30 Jan 2020	FR	Instruct-ERIC	Participant									
Instruct Italia kick-off conference	Launch event	10 Feb 2020	IT	Instruct-IT	Host									
Robotein launch	Launch event	14 Feb 2020	BE	Instruct-ULTRA/ Instruct-BE	Host									
Croatian Presidency Conference: European Research Infrastructures for a smarter future	Conference	18-19 Mar 2020	HR	Instruct-ERIC	Participant									
XVII Discussions in Structural Molecular Biology and 4 th User Meeting of CIISB	Conference Meeting	19-21 Mar 2020	CZ	Instruct-CZ	Participant									
Astbury Conversation	Conference	23-24 Mar 2020	GB	Instruct-ULTRA	Exhibition booth									
RI-VIS Symposium	Conference	23-24 Mar 2020	ZA	Instruct-ERIC	Joint host Presentation									
EMIM 2020	Conference	24-27 Mar 2020	GR	Instruct-CZ	Presentation									
Instruct-ERIC Council Meeting	Meeting	13 May 2020	NL	Instruct-ERIC	Host									

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Instruct-FI launch	Launch event	10 Jun 2020	FI	Instruct-ERIC/Instruct-FI	Host									
PCISBIO Day	Meeting	29 Jun 2020	PT	Instruct-ERIC	Presentation									
CTLS Congress 2020	Conference	30 Jun - 2 Jul 2020	PT	Instruct-ERIC	Presentation									
FEBS 2020	Conference	4-9 Jul 2020	SI	Instruct-ULTRA	Presentation Exhibition booth									
ICE Meeting	Networking event	Jul 2020	GB	Instruct-ULTRA	Joint host									
EMC 2020	Conference	23-28 Aug 2020	DK	Instruct-ULTRA	Presentation Exhibition booth									
EFMC-ISMC 2020	Conference	6-10 Sep 2020	CH	Instruct-ULTRA	Presentation Exhibition booth									
A celebration of Instruct-ERIC: achievements, impact and expanding ambitions	Reception	16 Sep 2020	BE	Instruct-ULTRA/ Instruct-ERIC	Host									
4 th Instruct Workshop on CryoEM Best Practices	Workshop	28-29 Sep 2020	GB	Instruct-ULTRA / Instruct-UK	Host									
Instruct/Calipso Industry Event	Networking event	30 Sep 2020	GB	Instruct-ULTRA	Joint host									
ICRI 2020	Conference	30 Sep – 1 Oct 2020	CA	Instruct-ERIC	Participant									
Instruct-ERIC Council Meeting	Meeting	15 Oct 2020	GB	Instruct-ERIC	Host									
Czech Day for European Research	Conference	30 Oct 2020	CZ	Instruct-CZ	Presentation									
Day of National Research Infrastructures, Czech Republic 2020	Conference	Nov 2020	CZ	Instruct-CZ	Presentation									

It is clear that Instruct-ULTRA has set out on a very ambitious stakeholder conference and meeting schedule. During RP2, Instruct-ULTRA participated in over 55 events and plans are already in place for participation in 25 events during RP3. Other events will be scheduled for the upcoming year as time and budget allows.

3. Description of events by stakeholder type

A description of each event in the stakeholders' calendar is listed below, grouped by stakeholder type. Where an event reaches multiple stakeholders, details are given in the text, although the event is only appearing once in the descriptions.

3.1 Policy makers and funders

3.1.1 Day of National Research Infrastructures

Date: November 2018, 2019, 2020 **Location:** Ostrava and Prague, Czech Republic

Audience: Czech ministry and ESFRI representatives, Czech national research infrastructures from all thematic fields

Summary: This event brings the Czech Research infrastructures community together on an annual basis to discuss various aspects of Research infrastructures. Instruct-CZ regularly presents its activities via poster and presentation or participation in the panel discussion.

Outcomes: Visibility of Instruct in research infrastructures community in the Czech Republic.

3.1.2 Instruct Biennial Structural Biology Conference 2019

Date: 22-24 May 2019 **Location:** Madrid, Spain

Audience: Policy makers and funders, industry, structural biology community, life science community, other research infrastructures, Instruct users.

Summary: The Instruct Biennial Structural Biology Conference draws an international audience of scientists wanting to share in the latest findings in cutting-edge, integrative structural biology, and the emerging technologies that are making an impact in life science research.

Outcomes: The Instruct Biennial Structural Biology Conference in 2019 was attended by scientists at all stages of their career. Numerous distinguished scientists came to support the event and demonstrated the importance of Instruct through impactful talks on their research. The event was also an opportunity to develop Instruct's industry partnerships: as well as talks from scientists working in industry, a number of the conference's sponsors hosted a booth at the event, and a representative from ThermoFisher gave a talk on Cryo-EM.

The conference was also attended by ministry representatives from Spain, with Prof Rafael Rodrigo Montero (Secretario General de Coordinación de Política Científica, Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación y Universidades) opening the event. Support from influential

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stakeholders, such as ministry representatives, has been key for leverage of structural funds in Spain.

3.1.3 Women in Science Workshop

Date: 22 May 2019 **Location:** Madrid, Spain

Audience: Policy makers and funders, industry, structural biology community, life science community, other research infrastructures, Instruct users.

Summary: The Women in Science Workshop was hosted by Instruct-ULTRA as a satellite event to the Instruct Biennial Structural Biology Conference 2019. The workshop (which was oversubscribed at 90 attendees) was a celebration of trailblazing women in structural biology, with talks from leading women scientists in industry and academia, and discussions about how Instruct-ERIC can support our community to progress in their careers. The programme included talks, a panel discussion, small group Q&A, and a drinks and tapas reception.

Outcomes: By stimulating discussion and action on the topic of Women in Science, the workshop provided an important opportunity to engage with the Spanish ministry. Prof Elena Domínguez, Vice President International Affairs at the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) provided a welcome address and reflected on the progress of female scientists in Spain. The workshop also fostered Instruct's industry connections, with Dr Ilaria Ferlenghi of GSK Vaccines, Italy, invited to give a talk from the perspective of women working in industry.

3.1.4 Instruct Sustainability Workshop

Date: 10 October 2019 **Location:** Brussels, Belgium

Audience: Policy makers and funders, government science ministries of potential member countries, EU/ESFRI, structural biology community, life science community, other research infrastructures.

Summary: The Instruct-ERIC sustainability workshop drew together experts from the European Commission, ESFRI, national policy units, research infrastructures, and Instruct-ERIC leadership. Coordinated by the Instruct-ULTRA project team, the workshop looked at the context of Horizon Europe (HE) and the task of KPI development and evaluation, before analysing sustainability from four angles: financial stability; continued excellence; cutting edge technology and tools; and communication.

Outcomes: Reflecting on the presentations and discussions, a number of areas of action were identified in Instruct's progress towards sustainability, including Instruct's funding model, communication with stakeholders, and maintaining excellence.

3.1.5 Instruct-ERIC Stakeholders Reception

Date: 16 September 2020 **Location:** Brussels, Belgium

Audience: Policy makers and funders, government science ministries of potential member countries, EU/ESFRI, life science community.

Summary: Instruct-ULTRA will be sponsoring a special event for Instruct-ERIC to strengthen its connections with its stakeholders, funders and policy makers. The event will celebrate Instruct's notable successes and will help to nurture relationships with influential stakeholders, in order to ensure Instruct's sustainability. In addition, the stakeholder reception will be a good opportunity for Instruct-ERIC to invite ministries from all the countries where discussions are taking place towards country membership.

3.2 Government science ministries of potential member countries

3.2.1 Instruct-ERIC meeting at the Solaris synchrotron

Date: 9 July 2019 **Location:** Krakow, Poland

Audience: Government science ministries of potential member countries, structural biology community, life science community.

Summary: The FEBS Congress 2019 was used as an opportunity for Instruct-ULTRA to host a meeting with leading scientists and ministry representatives from Poland to lay the groundwork for future Instruct Membership. Instruct-ULTRA was invited to visit the national synchrotron facility in Poland in order to participate in presentations and discussions relating to Polish membership of Instruct and a potential Polish Centre application.

Outcomes: 25 leading scientists in Poland have expressed support for country membership of Instruct-ERIC. Instruct-ULTRA staff are now in active discussions with a core group of scientists who are working to develop a proposal for the Polish ministry of science towards Instruct-ERIC membership. It is hoped to offer an open call to Polish scientists for test access to Instruct facilities, funded by Instruct-ULTRA, during RP3 if there is time before the end of the project.

3.2.2 Instruct-ERIC Meeting with Slovenian Ministry of Science

Date: 4-6 September 2019 **Location:** Ljubljana, Slovenia

Audience: Government science ministries of potential member countries.

Summary: Prof Ray Owens (P2) and Naomi Gray (P2) were invited by Prof Gregor Anderluh and Prof Marjetka Podobnik to a meeting with three members of the Slovenian ministry of education, science and sport to discuss Instruct-ERIC membership.

Outcomes: Instruct-ULTRA has a good understanding of the Slovenian roadmap and pathway to membership of new research infrastructures. Prof Marjetka Podobnik is taking the lead to develop a proposal for national membership of Instruct-ERIC, supported by staff from Instruct-ULTRA. It will be necessary to build up the national structural biology community, for example with a national conference, and to demonstrate national support for the endeavour. It is hoped to offer an open call to Slovenian scientists for test access to Instruct facilities during RP3 if time allows.

3.2.3 Instruct-ERIC Meeting with Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR)

Date: 17 January 2020 **Location:** Delhi, India

Audience: Funders and policies makers of potential member countries, structural biology community, life science community

Summary: Prof Dave Stuart (P2), Prof Joel Sussman (P11) and Naomi Gray (P2) were invited to the headquarters of the ICMR to discuss collaborations with India.

Outcomes: There is a strong desire from all institutes within the ICMR to formally collaborate with Instruct-ERIC, and the ICMR leadership have offered to sign an agreement with Instruct-ERIC which would cover all research institutes and universities within India. The ICMR requested that test membership (formalised by signing of an MoU) would be limited to 2 years, in order to progress to full international membership of Instruct-ERIC, which would include the ICMR paying the membership subscription. Test membership would include one in country training course taught by Instruct-ERIC academics and an open call for Indian scientists to visit Instruct facilities if time allows.

3.3 EU / ESFRI

3.3.1 ESFRI workshop: Monitoring of infrastructures, periodic update of Landmarks, use of KPIs

Date: 19-20 November 2018 **Location:** Milan, Italy

Audience: ESFRI Forum members, members of ESFRI Monitoring working group, representatives of ESFRI projects

Summary: This ESFRI workshop was aimed at discussing possible approaches to monitoring of ESFRI Landmarks in the future and served as a starting point of discussions of the newly established ESFRI Monitoring Working Group. Ondřej Hradil from Instruct-CZ gave a presentation on its view of evaluations taking place at different levels of distributed infrastructures and suggestions for the ESFRI approach on behalf of Instruct.

Outcomes: Contribution towards discussions about Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and sustainability.

3.3.2 Bulgarian Presidency of the Council of the EU Flagship Conference: "Research Infrastructures beyond 2020 – sustainable and effective ecosystem for science and society"

Date: July 2018 and 2020 **Location:** Ghent, Belgium; Lisbon, Portugal

Audience: EU/ESFRI, national ministry representatives, policy makers

Summary: Official Bulgarian presidency event devoted to current trends in policy related to Research Infrastructures with major focus on sustainability of Research Infrastructures.

Outcomes: Visibility of Instruct-ERIC in Research infrastructures community, understanding of current policy trends in the field of Research infrastructures, communication with stakeholders.

3.3.3 ICRI2018 – International Conference on Research Infrastructures

Date: 12-14 September 2018 **Location:** Vienna, Austria

Audience: EU/ESFRI, national ministry representatives, policy makers

Summary: This event brings together representatives of institutional core facilities in the field of life sciences (many of them related to structural biology), industrial representatives are present as well. Various aspects of core facility and Research Infrastructures operations are discussed.

Outcomes: Visibility of Instruct-ERIC in the Research Infrastructures community.

3.3.4 ESFRI Strategy Report on RIs

Date: 25 September 2019 **Location:** Brussels, Belgium

Audience: EU/ESFRI, other research infrastructures.

Summary: This event presented the process and content of update of ESFRI Roadmap as well as the monitoring steps ESFRI envisages for current ESFRI Landmarks. Ondřej Hradil and Susan Daenke represented Instruct at the event.

Outcomes: Understanding of current evaluation processes within ESFRI and reflecting on their impact on Instruct. Discussions with policy stakeholders from European Commission and other Research infrastructures.

3.4 Industry

3.4.1 Protein Structure Determination in Industry (PSDI) 2018

Date: 11-13 November 2018 **Location:** Versailles, France

Audience: Industry, life science community, structural biology community.

Summary: Dr Ludo Renault from Instruct-NL (P13) gave a scientific talk about CryoEM, including the services offered to industry by Instruct-ERIC, and was invited to join a roundtable discussion about how CryoEM could be used more widely within an industrial setting.

Outcomes: CryoEM is an emerging trend for industry, and as a result of this talk and roundtable discussion, Instruct-ERIC was positioned as a key player in European CryoEM. This will inevitably lead to more enquiries to the Instruct centres from industry clients.

3.4.2 Women in Biotech

Date: 13 June 2019 **Location:** Oxford, UK

Audience: Industry, life science community, structural biology community.

Summary: The aim of the event was to inspire and support women to take up founding roles in industry, through discussion and networking sessions.

Outcomes: Instruct-ULTRA attended the local Women in Biotech event in order to engage with the entrepreneur community in Oxford. The event proved to be useful in understanding some of the challenges facing biotech start-ups, and the networking element was an opportunity to informally introduce Instruct-ERIC to scientists working in the life science industry in Oxfordshire.

3.4.3 Instruct for Industry

Date: 27 June 2019 **Location:** Harwell, UK

Audience: Industry.

Summary: As part of Deliverable 5.3, Instruct-ULTRA hosted a pilot networking event in the UK to increase engagement with small- to medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in life science.

Outcomes: The event proved immensely valuable in developing new contacts in industry and associated networks, and has since generated new industrial users for Instruct. It is hoped that the ULTRA-led event will serve as a template for similar industry outreach events across Instruct's Centres.

3.4.4 Rendez-vous CARNOT (French tradeshow)

Date: 16-17 October 2019 **Location:** Paris, France

Audience: Industry, life science community.

Summary: Darren Hart and Auriane Denis-Meyere manned an exhibition booth promoting the French Infrastructure for Integrated Structural biology (FRISBI) including access for national and EU users to Instruct-ERIC FR1 and FR2 centres in Strasbourg and Grenoble respectively. The annual Rendez-Vous CARNOT is a tradeshow that brings together businesses and seeks to increase partnering opportunities. In 2019, the national and EU infrastructures were invited to present their services and access modes.

Outcomes: Several companies have expressed interest in services and collaborative projects. Discussions are ongoing.

3.4.5 Meet in Italy for Life Science

Date: 16-18 October 2019 **Location:** Trieste, IT

Audience: industry, life science community.

Summary: This was the 6th edition of this meeting that is attracting a higher and higher number of industries (over 250). Instruct-ULTRA sponsored an Instruct-IT scientist, Marco Fragai who had the opportunity to meet several SMEs in the brokerage event and present services available at Instruct-ERIC.

Outcomes: Some of the companies showed great interest in the service provision and some possible request of service or collaboration are under discussion.

3.4.6 Protein Structure Determination in Industry (PSDI) Meeting 2019

Date: 3-5 November 2019 **Location:** Cambridge, UK

Audience: industry, structural biology community, life science community.

Summary: The PSDI meeting is a long-running meeting for structural biologists working in industry. Instruct-ULTRA sponsored an Instruct-UK scientist, Dr Andrew Quigley, to attend PSDI to give a presentation about the structural biology of membrane proteins and the technology available from Instruct-ERIC.

Outcomes: Interactions with industry representatives indicated a general awareness of Instruct-ERIC in the context of services for academic research, however few were aware of Instruct's services for industry. Feedback from the event has proven useful in helping to develop Instruct's industry engagement and has highlighted a need to promote this more effectively.

3.4.7 MipTec/BASEL LIFE Conference

Date: 9-12 September 2019 **Location:** Basel, Switzerland

Audience: Industry, life science community.

Summary: The MipTec exhibition, which coincides with the BASEL LIFE conference, is a platform to exhibit life science technologies and services to scientists in industrially relevant, translational, basic and applied research and development. Instruct-ULTRA shared a joint booth with EU-OPENSREEN, with the aim of generating new industry users for Instruct-ERIC.

Outcomes: There were expressions of interest in Instruct from industry attendees. However, many scientists were working in the pharmaceutical industry, and it was apparent that there is a need to demonstrate how structural biology can be of benefit to drug discovery (eg structure-based drug design). Many attendees of the conference were from Switzerland (not currently a Member country) and therefore ineligible for funded access to Instruct services. Nonetheless, there was considerable interest in Instruct services from both student scientists and PIs, which might incentivise application for Instruct membership.

3.4.8 Interfaces in Cryo-EM (ICE) networking event

Date: July 2020 **Location:** Oxford, UK

Audience: Industry, structural biology community, life science community.

Summary: The second ICE networking event will be jointly hosted by the Instruct-ERIC (through the Instruct-ULTRA project), the Rosalind Franklin Institute, Vertex Pharmaceuticals and the Diamond Light Source. The event seeks to build a community of academic and industry researchers who are interested in cryo-EM, to foster pre-competitive

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knowledge sharing, collaborations, and to promote investment in cryo-EM infrastructure and future applications.

3.4.9 Joint Instruct-ERIC and Calipso industry event

Date: 30 September 2020

Location: London, UK

Audience: Industry.

Summary: Instruct-ULTRA will be hosting a one-day industry event, jointly funded by Calipso (a project for open access to accelerator-based light sources) through the Diamond Light Source. The event will comprise scientific talks and networking, using the narrative of the drug development pipeline to demonstrate what large scale facilities and research infrastructures can offer to industry. It is hoped that the event will generate new industry partnerships for Instruct-ERIC.

3.5 Structural Biology Community

Many Instruct-ULTRA partners have organised national conferences to engage with their local structural biology community, including FRISBI, CIISB and Instruct-ITALIA. The purpose of such events is to build up national life science communities, to create opportunities for collaboration, and to promote Instruct-ERIC services and technologies to early-career researchers.

In addition, Instruct-ULTRA has piloted a launch event for new Instruct-ERIC research sites. The first of these was hosted in Leeds (UK) on 25 November 2019, to mark the launch of the Astbury Biostructure Laboratory as an Instruct-UK research site. At the event, facility staff showcased the cryo-EM, NMR and mass spectrometry technologies of the Astbury Centre, and two keynote lectures demonstrated the expertise of the Astbury Biostructure Laboratory and the power of integrative methods in structural biology. The event was attended by researchers and students from across the University of Leeds, and the Vice Chancellor of the University accepted a commemorative plaque from Instruct. The event provided important recognition and publicity for the award of a new Instruct research site, and is to be replicated for future launches, including the upcoming inauguration of the Robotein facility to Instruct-BE.

3.6 Life Science Community

A key focus of Instruct-ULTRA is to reach out to scientists in the wider life science community in order to demonstrate the complementarity of structural biology techniques to life science research. A campaign of events targeting a broad range of life science domains (neuroscience, virology, biophysics, cell biology, imaging, chemical biology, medical research etc.) was planned for Reporting Periods 2 and 3. Such activities typically centre around conference participation, including a session about European Research Infrastructures and a booth in the exhibition hall. In some cases, Instruct-ULTRA's participation at conferences is jointly shared with closely affiliated research infrastructures, such as EU-OPENSOURCE² and Euro-Biolmaging³.

² A European Research Infrastructure (RI) focusing on chemical biology <https://www.eu-openscreen.eu>

³ A European RI in the area of medical and cellular imaging <https://www.eurobioimaging.eu>

3.6.1 CTLS Congress

Date: 2-4 Jul 2018; 30 Jun – 2 Jul 2020 **Location:** Ghent, Belgium; Lisbon, Portugal

Audience: managers and technicians of life sciences related core facilities from around Europe, industry

Summary: This event brings together representatives of institutional core facilities in the field of life sciences (many of them related to structural biology), industrial representatives are present as well. Various aspects of core facility and Research Infrastructures operations are discussed.

Outcomes: Visibility of Instruct-ERIC in the context of facility management, emerging technologies, knowledge exchange and best practices in life science research infrastructures.

3.6.2 HyThaBio conference

Date: 27-31 Jan 2019 **Location:** Grenoble, France

Audience: life science community, structural biology community.

Summary: A week-long workshop on biophysical methods for life scientists (mainly students and postdocs). A special seminar by Darren Hart was dedicated to promoting Instruct-ERIC user access within this user community. The aim was to make attendees aware of the activities and funding opportunities of Instruct-ERIC.

Outcomes: Better knowledge of Instruct to encourage good access projects being submitted through ARIA.

3.6.3 AILM2019 conference

Date: 29 Mar - 5 Apr 2019 **Location:** Grenoble, France

Audience: life science community, structural biology community

Summary: A week-long workshop on isotopic labelling methods for life scientists (mainly students and postdocs). A special seminar by Darren Hart was dedicated to promoting Instruct-ERIC user access within this user community. The aim was to make attendees aware of the activities and funding opportunities of Instruct-ERIC.

Outcomes: Better knowledge of Instruct to encourage good access projects being submitted through ARIA.

3.6.4 European Congress of Virology (ESV)

Date: 28 April - 1 May 2019 **Location:** Rotterdam, The Netherlands

Audience: life science community, structural biology community

Summary: At the ESV conference, Instruct-ULTRA presented at the “European Research Infrastructures: How can we help you?” special session with a scientific talk from Dr Tom Bowden (P2) and an introduction to Instruct services by Naomi Gray (P2). The main aim of attending ECV was to demonstrate the applicability of structural biology, and hence Instruct services, to the wider life science community.

Outcomes: Instruct-ERIC services promoted to the audience of over 60 people, and good relationships established with other research infrastructures / projects participating at the event (ERINHA, EVA, Euro-Biolmaging and Infravec2), who are all keen to work together for future conferences in virology.

3.6.5 Microscience Microscopy Congress (MMC)

Date: 1-4 July 2019 **Location:** Manchester, UK

Audience: life science community.

Summary: Instruct-ULTRA hosted an Instruct-ERIC booth in the 'Newcomers' area of the MMC exhibition hall.

Outcomes: Conference attendees (from the UK and abroad) were from a wide range of scientific backgrounds, including material, physical and life sciences. Interactions with attendees identified a largely untapped but receptive audience of life scientists. Whilst few people who stopped by the booth had prior knowledge of Instruct-ERIC, many expressed their interest and surprise at the funded access and training that is offered by Instruct. More broadly, the conference highlighted the large potential user base for Instruct outside of structural biology.

3.6.6 Federation of European Biochemical Societies (FEBS) Congress

Date: 5-9 July 2019 **Location:** Krakow, Poland

Audience: Government science ministries of potential member countries, structural biology community, life science community, other research infrastructures, Instruct users.

Summary: The FEBS congress is aimed at scientists in Europe and neighbouring regions, working in the molecular life sciences. FEBS was identified as a particularly appropriate conference for Instruct to attend, given the significant overlap with structural biology. Instruct-ULTRA made significant efforts to ensure a strong Instruct-ERIC presence at the FEBS congress.

Outcomes: On behalf of Instruct-ERIC, Instruct-ULTRA participated in a joint Research Infrastructure booth with EU-OPENSOURCE, Euro-BioImaging and CORBEL. Instruct received significant interest at the congress and interactions at the booth generated numerous new contacts and potential users for Instruct. Instruct-ULTRA also presented a 15-minute overview of Instruct-ERIC at the symposium: 'Using international research infrastructures to boost your science', which had an audience of approximately 120 people. Instruct-ERIC was also acknowledged by Instruct Centre staff during their talks in the 'Integrative approaches to structural and synthetic biology' symposium.

3.6.7 European Biophysical Societies Association (EBSA) Conference

Date: 20-26 July 2019 **Location:** Madrid, Spain

Audience: Life science community.

Summary: Instruct-ULTRA hosted an Instruct Structural Biology Symposium, which included scientific talks from Instruct staff Prof Marc Baldus (P13), Prof Rob Gilbert (P2), Prof Jose Maria Carazo (P8) and an introduction to Instruct services by Naomi Gray (P2). The talks demonstrated the complementarity of structural biology techniques and how these can be used in an integrative way in order to answer important scientific questions.

Outcomes: Instruct-ERIC science and services promoted to the audience of over 250 scientists. Good relations were established with EBSA, which should lead to future invitations to lead a similar symposium in future conferences.

3.6.8 American Society for Cell Biology (ASCB) and European Molecular Biology Organization (EMBO) meeting

Date: 8-11 December 2019 **Location:** Washington DC, USA

Audience: Life science community.

Summary: The ASCB EMBO meeting is a conference for cell biology. Instruct-ULTRA hosted an Instruct-ERIC booth in the non-profit area of the exhibition hall, and gave a fifteen minute presentation about Instruct as part of a joint session with EU-OPENSSCREEN, Euro-Biolmaging and Infrafrontier, entitled 'How to boost your research project with the support of international research infrastructures'.

Outcomes: Instruct-ULTRA's participation at ASCB-EMBO aimed to generate new users for Instruct from the cell biology community. As few conference attendees undertook structural biology in their research, it was important to be proactive and engage with conference goers in order to explain how structural biology might enhance their research. This proved to be a productive approach that generated a number of new potential users for Instruct.

The conference also proved to be an excellent opportunity to develop Instruct's relationship with the American national cryo-EM service centres, which are based at the New York Structural Biology Center, the Oregon Health & Science University in Portland - in partnership with the Pacific Northwest National Laboratory in Washington, and the SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory at Stanford University in California.

3.6.9 European Molecular Imaging Meeting (EMIM)

Date: 24-27 Mar 2020 **Location:** Thessaloniki, Greece

Audience: Life science community.

Summary: The ESMI represents and advocates imaging science for knowledge exchange covering basic sciences, translational aspects as well as clinical applications. Instruct-ULTRA will be funding an Instruct Centre CZ scientist to represent Instruct-ERIC by presentation during a joint Research Infrastructures session.

3.6.10 Federation of European Biochemical Societies (FEBS) Congress

Date: 4-9 July 2020 **Location:** Ljubljana, Slovenia

Audience: Policy makers and funders, structural biology community, life science community, other research infrastructures, Instruct users.

Summary: Following the success of the FEBS Congress in 2019, Instruct-ULTRA is negotiating for both a joint Research Infrastructure session and a booth with EU-OPENSSCREEN and Euro-Biolmaging. The conference is an excellent opportunity to inform Slovenian scientists of the funded research and training opportunities that are available through Instruct-ERIC.

3.6.11 European Federation for Medicinal Chemistry International Symposium on Medicinal Chemistry (EFMC-ISMC 2020)

Date: 6-10 September 2020 **Location:** Basel, Switzerland

Audience: Government science ministries of potential member countries, life science community.

Summary: EFMC-ISMC is a key conference in the field of medicinal chemistry and drug discovery, attracting approximately 1000 attendees from industry and academia. Instruct-ULTRA plans to host a joint booth with EU-OPENSSCREEN, and is in negotiation for a session that will include presentations about European Research Infrastructures. It is also intended that the conference will be an opportunity to meet with leading Swiss scientists to discuss interest in future Instruct membership.

3.7 Other research infrastructures

3.7.1 Public Awareness of Research Infrastructures (PARI) Conference

Date: 8-10 April 2019 **Location:** Harwell, UK

Audience: Other research infrastructures.

Summary: PARI is a hands-on forum for communications, public relations and engagement professionals to share their experiences and expertise. Instruct-ULTRA participated in workshops on communicating the importance of science to society. The event provided a useful platform to engage with other research infrastructures and organisations on the topic of communication.

Outcomes: Networking at this event led to some very productive connections with other life science networks, including with the STFC HealthTec Cluster, which develops local enterprise partnerships across the UK.

3.7.2 Research Infrastructure Communications and Engagement (RICE) working group meeting

Date: 11 April 2019 **Location:** Harwell, UK

Audience: Other research infrastructures.

Summary: The RICE working group meet to discuss best practices in public relation, communication and engagement of its member infrastructures and organisations.

Outcomes: Instruct-ULTRA represented Instruct-ERIC at the RICE meeting, facilitating Instruct membership of the RICE working group.

3.7.3 RI-VIS Workshop for Work Package 5: Communication Toolkit

Date: 1-2 October 2019 **Locations:** Paris, France

Summary: RI-VIS is a H2020-funded project that aims to establish working methods and tools for all research infrastructure to improve its visibility and impact. The workshop involved hands-on activities and discussions between communications professionals from different RIs, with the aim of developing resources for European RIs to integrate into their communication activities.

Outcomes: The discussions at the workshop facilitated the development of the RI-VIS Communication Toolkit, which contains tools, guidelines and resources for different types of communication, including RI websites and social media.

4. Summary and recommendations

Stakeholder engagement is crucial for the long-term sustainability of Instruct-ERIC, both to secure Instruct membership and to generate the scientific usership that vindicates such membership. Therefore, as well as developing and sustaining established partnerships, it is imperative that Instruct continues to grow its presence in international structural biology, whilst also reaching out to new user communities in the wider life science domain. To this end, Instruct-ULTRA has made significant efforts to arrange activities that reach out to a variety of Instruct stakeholders, including policy makers, science ministries, industry and research scientists. In parallel, ULTRA has also sought, or created opportunities to participate in the activities of other organisations and networks, where this is of mutual benefit to Instruct, the host, and the scientific community. ULTRA activities have targeted

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both member and non-member countries, and reach out across different fields in life science.

When engaging with influential stakeholders (such as policy makers, funders, science ministries, EU/ESFRI, and senior scientists) closed or exclusive events have been found most productive. These smaller meetings tend to facilitate more open and yet targeted conversations that, on numerous occasions, have made important strides towards new Instruct membership.

Large national and international conferences have proven successful at generating interest in Instruct-ERIC amongst potential user communities. Conference presentations about RIs and Instruct-ERIC tend to draw a larger audience when scheduled before or after a relevant scientific talk, or when part of a sponsored session. In this way, it is possible to capture a relevant audience that is unaware of Instruct, as well as those who are familiar with the RI. Besides conference presentations, exhibition booths have been effective for engagement with a large number of people - particularly those who would not otherwise attend an Instruct presentation (perhaps due to lack of awareness of the research infrastructure and/or the broader applicability of structural biology technologies in life science). Therefore, ULTRA recommends that future conference efforts by Instruct should aim to include both a presentation and a booth, as this strategy has proven highly effective in generating interest in Instruct services.

It is also important to consider the theme and location of the activities attended by Instruct. Conferences, such as FEBS, which have strong overlap with structural biology tend to have more receptive attendees that either know about Instruct-ERIC, or would be interested in the services offered. Attendees of conferences in other life science domains are often unaware of Instruct-ERIC, and tend not to have considered using structural biology in their research. Whilst it may take more effort to engage scientists working in the wider life science community, there is a large audience of potential Instruct users. With regards to location, events in Instruct Member countries tend to be more imminently fruitful due to the high proportion of national scientists who are eligible for funding. Nonetheless, events in non-member countries present an opportunity to garner support from the scientific community for future Instruct membership.